

Augmenting Systematic Literature Reviews: A Human-AI Collaborative Framework

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Abstract. While Systematic Literature Reviews (SLRs) are integral to research by synthesizing existing knowledge and guiding future inquiry, the exponential increase in academic publications presents significant challenges to traditional, manual review methods, notably regarding scalability, efficiency, and researcher workload. Recent advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly Large Language Models (LLMs), offer promising avenues for augmenting the SLR process. Nonetheless, integrating AI into literature reviews introduces methodological complexities, including maintaining accuracy, minimizing biases, and preserving scholarly rigor. To address these challenges, this paper introduces a structured AI-augmented SLR framework, systematically integrating AI capabilities into Wolfswinkel et al.'s [37] established Grounded Theory Literature Review Method. Our framework incorporates AI-driven relevance assessments, automated selection processes, and thematic content analysis, underpinned by rigorous human oversight to ensure reliability and interpretative validity. We empirically illustrate and evaluate our framework through a comparative study, replicating and extending a previously published human SLR. The evaluation assesses AI performance using key metrics such as type I and type II error rates across varying confidence thresholds. Results demonstrate substantial efficiency gains and effective accuracy in AI-assisted selection, highlighting the importance of carefully calibrated thresholds and continued human oversight. Our study contributes practical guidelines for effectively balancing AI automation with human scholarly judgment, offering a replicable methodological approach for researchers seeking to leverage AI capabilities without compromising methodological quality or academic integrity.

Keywords: Systematic Literature Review · Artificial Intelligence · Large Language Models · Research Augmentation · Human-AI Collaboration

1 Introduction

Systematic Literature Reviews (SLRs) are fundamental to research, providing structured methods for synthesizing existing knowledge, uncovering research

gaps, and setting directions for future investigations [36, 37]. However, traditional SLR methods face increasing challenges due to the exponential growth in academic literature [18]. Conventional manual approaches encompass comprehensive database searches, extensive article screening, detailed thematic analysis, and synthesis of insights, which are resource-intensive, laborious, and time-consuming [6]. As publication volumes surge, researchers increasingly struggle to maintain rigor and comprehensiveness within reasonable timeframes, highlighting the pressing need for more efficient methodologies [35, 24]. Moreover, rapidly evolving theories and technologies further underline the need for efficient SLR methodologies, as timely synthesis of literature is essential to maintain relevance and support ongoing research advancements [24].

Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly Large Language Models (LLMs), present promising avenues for augmenting and enhancing traditional SLR processes, as they can automate critical components, such as article retrieval, relevance assessment, duplicate removal, and preliminary thematic analysis [28, 38, 33, 12]. These capabilities offer significant potential to enhance the efficiency, consistency, and scalability of SLR processes, as recent hybrid methodologies combining AI-driven techniques with human oversight have demonstrated substantial reductions in manual effort and improved workflow effectiveness (e.g., in screening of articles [38], or data extraction [28]). Nevertheless, integrating AI into scholarly review processes introduces methodological challenges regarding accuracy, reliability, potential biases, and the preservation of scholarly rigor [25, 35, 30]. Despite notable progress, most AI-assisted literature reviews still lack structured methodological frameworks explicitly designed to integrate AI systematically with transparent human oversight, often remaining qualitative or exploratory in nature [30, 24].

Addressing these methodological challenges, this paper proposes an SLR framework which is augmented by AI. Drawing upon the established Grounded Theory Literature Review Method by Wolfswinkel et al. [37], our framework systematically incorporates AI assistance at critical stages of the SLR process. These include automated article retrieval, relevance classification using LLMs, and AI-supported thematic analysis through open and axial coding. In this way, we conduct research on the capacities of AI, covering the automation of pre-defined, repetitive tasks [32], the analysis of large data sources [10, 1], and the clusters of retrieved information [17]. The framework emphasizes rigorous human oversight and iterative validation at every step, ensuring methodological robustness and scholarly rigor while effectively leveraging AI's capabilities.

Therefore, this study advances the field by systematically integrating AI into a structured SLR framework. We illustrate the practical application and evaluate the methodological rigor of the proposed AI-augmented SLR framework through an empirical comparative case study, replicating and extending a previously conducted human-led SLR [5]. By directly comparing AI-assisted approaches to traditional manual methods within a clearly defined research context, we systematically assess the accuracy, thematic alignment, efficiency gains, and practical trade-offs associated with AI integration.

2 Theoretical Background

With knowledge production accelerating at a tremendous speed while remaining fragmented and interdisciplinary, SLRs are more relevant than ever, for researchers and practitioners alike [31]. Established concept-centric and input-process-output frameworks have significantly shaped how researchers systematically select and synthesize academic literature for SLRs [36, 21]. Additional methodological refinements include the five-phase Grounded Theory Literature Review Method by Wolfswinkel et al. [37], which emphasizes rigorous iterative thematic analysis. Despite these methodological advances, researchers increasingly struggle with practical challenges arising from exponential growth in academic publications, difficulties in unbiased study selection, and maintaining reproducibility [35, 37].

Many of these challenges can be addressed by integrating AI into the SLR process, since AI (and particularly LLMs) has already demonstrated transformative capabilities across various analytical tasks and contexts, including text summarization [2], sentiment analysis [7, 20], thematic classification [16, 22, 9], and general creative contexts [14]. Recent research has begun to explore these applications within literature reviews by demonstrating the potential of AI to support tasks such as identifying and filtering relevant evidence [24], thematic coding [29], real-time literature searching [13], and drafting summarizations [15], showing that these techniques can significantly reduce manual workload while maintaining acceptable accuracy [28, 27]. Additionally, recent classifications have highlighted numerous ready-to-use AI tools supporting the entire SLR process, from search to presentation [3].

However, these existing solutions typically lack systematic empirical evaluation regarding methodological rigor, epistemic implications, and effectiveness compared to traditional human-led approaches, especially for complex tasks like conceptual synthesis and thematic analysis. More recently, attention has shifted toward generative AI and LLMs, such as ChatGPT, to support deeper conceptual analysis and synthesis in literature reviews [30, 38, 4]. Exploratory studies have illustrated generative AI’s potential, while emphasizing limitations like hallucinations, interpretive inaccuracy, and the necessity of sustained human oversight [30, 38, 11]. Although hybrid workflows combining human judgment with LLM-assisted screening have shown promise [38], fully autonomous reviews remain impractical due to ongoing challenges in interpretive fidelity and methodological rigor. Alongside technical advancements, critical perspectives have examined the epistemic and methodological implications of AI adoption in scholarly review processes [25, 34]. These discussions highlight that while AI offers potential in streamlining review tasks, it also risks shifting foundational scholarly values, including interpretive transparency, argumentative coherence, and epistemic accountability [25, 35, 34]. Structured frameworks clearly defining human-AI collaboration have thus been advocated to maintain scholarly rigor and reproducibility [35].

Extending beyond that, we propose an AI-augmented SLR framework, integrating AI capabilities across the full SLR process, from search and selection

through thematic analysis and synthesis. Our approach explicitly delineates human and AI responsibilities, emphasizing rigorous validation through quantitative and qualitative empirical comparisons with a traditional human-led SLR.

3 Methodology

We propose an AI-augmented SLR framework based on Wolfswinkel et al.’s approach [37], comprising the five phases Define, Search, Select, Analyze, and Present. The framework systematically incorporates AI, particularly LLMs, to enhance efficiency while maintaining rigorous human oversight. Figure 1 summarizes the proposed approach, highlighting AI’s role in each sub-stage. While AI provides substantial assistance throughout various review stages, human researchers maintain ultimate responsibility for critical interpretation, validation, and methodological rigor. Therefore, scholars employing this framework should proactively and critically evaluate AI-generated outputs, ensuring accuracy and appropriateness, and remain mindful not to inadvertently shift workload toward tasks requiring more substantial human judgment.

Fig. 1. AI-augmented SLR framework (adapted from [37]). Mainly human-driven (blue), mainly machine-driven (green), and collaborative (yellow) activities.

The *Define* phase establishes the foundation for the SLR by setting precise boundaries and objectives [37]. This phase is crucially human-driven to ensure

that the review aligns closely with the study’s research questions and scholarly standards. Initially, researchers define clear and explicit inclusion and exclusion criteria that guide the review process. While LLMs or AI tools could suggest potentially relevant criteria based on patterns found in prior SLRs, these AI-generated suggestions serve only as preliminary input. Human researchers critically review, modify, and finalize these criteria based on expert knowledge and the specific research objectives. Similarly, identifying relevant research fields and selecting appropriate academic outlets and databases remains primarily human-driven. Although AI may perform bibliometric or literature analyses to highlight potentially relevant research fields or frequently used academic databases, the final decision on the scope and sources remains under direct human oversight. Human researchers validate AI-generated insights against domain knowledge, relevance, and practical considerations. Finally, in determining specific search terms, researchers maintain ultimate control. AI-supported tools and LLMs can propose synonyms, variations, or alternative keyword combinations to optimize search queries, but human researchers carefully assess these recommendations through iterative refinement and quality testing, ensuring comprehensive yet focused retrieval of relevant literature.

In the *Search* phase [37], AI-driven automation performs database queries and literature retrieval through the use of APIs or web scraping scripts, using selected academic databases. Automated searches help enhance comprehensiveness, ensuring consistent retrieval across multiple sources and substantially reducing manual workload. However, human oversight remains critical, e.g., controlling completeness.

In the *Select* phase [37], AI-assisted filtering supports the systematic refinement of the retrieved corpus to efficiently identify relevant literature. Initially, automated scripts identify and remove duplicate records across multiple databases, after which human reviewers conduct a brief validation to correct potential inaccuracies in automated duplicate detection. Subsequently, LLMs perform preliminary relevance assessments based on titles and abstracts, providing detailed justifications accompanied by confidence ratings (percentages) for each paper. To quantitatively assess the accuracy of AI-driven classifications, human reviewers then independently validate a representative subset (approximately 20%), akin to assessing intercoder reliability (ICR) commonly used in qualitative research [26]. Such validation ensures transparency, systematicity, and robustness in the relevance assessment, facilitating calibration of AI selection thresholds to balance inclusiveness and specificity. Additionally, LLMs further augment full-text relevance screening by automatically extracting relevant text excerpts and assigning individual confidence scores. AI tools can also assist with citation analysis by identifying potentially relevant forward and backward citations based on title and abstract content. Despite this substantial automation, human researchers retain ultimate responsibility for final verification and correctness, ensuring relevance, accuracy, and thematic alignment with the study’s objectives.

In the *Analyze* phase [37], AI can facilitate thematic and conceptual synthesis. AI-driven open coding rapidly extracts relevant excerpts and identifies preliminary thematic patterns (open codes) from the literature corpus. Subsequently, axial coding (i.e., grouping related open codes into broader conceptual categories) is supported by semantic clustering, co-occurrence analysis, and AI-driven recommendations for thematic consolidation. Human researchers iteratively review and refine these AI-generated thematic structures to ensure they are both theoretically sound and contextually appropriate. The final step, selective coding, involves the human-led development of a cohesive, overarching conceptual framework, with AI offering supplemental insights by highlighting connections among themes, summarizing key relationships, and suggesting conceptual syntheses to enrich the analytical process.

During the final *Present* phase [37], AI supports clear communication and effective visualization of the review’s outcomes. Automated scripts and visualization tools generate illustrative graphics such as thematic maps, e.g. [8], word clouds, e.g. [23], and histograms, e.g. [19], facilitating the identification and communication of literature trends, concept prominence, and thematic relationships. Given that the underlying data (e.g., selected papers, thematic codes, publication years) is available in a structured format, LLMs or AI tools can automatically generate a variety of meaningful visualizations, such as publication trends over time, concept distributions across studies, or thematic co-occurrence maps. Since these visualizations are grounded in validated and structured data, the risk of hallucinations is inherently minimized. In this context, AI does not create new content but rather assists in the automated generation of accurate and customizable visual representations, allowing human researchers to focus on interpretative analysis and presentation quality. Additionally, LLMs assist in structuring the manuscript by suggesting logical narrative sequences, organizing key findings, and drafting initial summaries. Despite these AI contributions, human researchers retain final responsibility for the manuscript’s narrative structure, clarity, coherence, and scholarly quality, carefully reviewing and refining AI-generated content to ensure adherence to rigorous academic standards (e.g., in terms of AI authorship and allowed machine contributions). While LLMs can produce plausible-sounding but fabricated content, commonly referred to as hallucinations, our method actively mitigates this risk through structured prompting and grounded generation. By always providing contextual input based on retrieved and validated source texts (akin to retrieval-augmented generation), the LLM’s outputs are anchored in real data. Nonetheless, human researchers must still verify the factual accuracy and interpretive validity of any AI-generated contributions to ensure the final synthesis includes only verifiable sources.

4 Evaluation and Comparative Study

To illustrate and assess the applicability of our proposed AI-augmented SLR framework, we conducted a comparative case study with a previously published human-led SLR [5] serving as a detailed baseline. This specific SLR was chosen

for its topical relevance, publicly documented process, and the authors’ full access to its dataset (including search strategies, selection criteria, and thematic coding). This comprehensive access enabled a fine-grained, step-by-step comparison essential for this initial validation of our detailed framework, an approach often not feasible with more generic benchmarks that may lack such process transparency for a qualitative methodology like Wolfswinkel et al.’s [37].

Fig. 2. Example of suggestions by ChatGPT 4o for constructing an SLR search string using keywords linked by Boolean operators based on the research question.

The *Define* phase sets a critical foundation for the SLR. While we explicitly replicated the human-led SLR’s original research definition, including inclusion/exclusion criteria, research scope, selected databases (ACM Digital Library, AISel, IEEE Xplore), and exact search terms, to ensure methodological comparability, we also explored potential AI support for augmenting this phase through LLMs: We prompted an LLM to generate a search string structured with Boolean operators (Figure 2). The resulting output demonstrated the model’s capacity to serve as an effective “sparring partner,” particularly for individual or early-stage researchers who may lack immediate feedback when developing search strategies. The LLM-generated string offered broad coverage of AI-related concepts, sustainability criteria, smart home contexts, and explicitly stated requirements.

Table 2 highlights key differences between the AI-generated and human-designed search strings. While both addressed core themes such as AI, sustainability, and smart environments, the human-designed string emphasized application contexts and analytical frameworks (e.g., **app***, **platform***, **guideline***), whereas the LLM proposed a wider vocabulary of requirement-related terms and a more expansive understanding of smart environments, including phrases like ambient intelligence and connected home.

These differences underscore the complementary value of AI-generated suggestions: LLMs can enhance terminological breadth and conceptual variety, help-

ing researchers surface relevant alternatives they may not have otherwise considered. However, to maintain methodological rigor, any such suggestions must be critically reviewed, refined, and validated by human researchers to ensure alignment with the specific research goals and domain-specific conventions.

For the *Search* phase, we recommend employing APIs and automated scripts for efficient and consistent literature retrieval across multiple academic databases. Accordingly, we implemented scripts for automatic literature retrieval and tested their functionality, with only minor discrepancies between the sets, attributable to database-specific indexing differences or retrieval settings.

Starting from the *Select* phase, we exclusively used GPT-4o-mini via the OpenAI API, prompting the model to return responses in a structured JSON format. Table 3 gives an overview of the prompts employed in our AI-augmented SLR. This ensured all outputs, including relevance justifications and confidence scores, were machine-readable and automatically processable in subsequent steps, eliminating the risk of hallucinations or invented sources. Due to its speed and very low cost, we selected GPT-4o-mini, enabling the complete AI-augmented SLR process to be conducted for under \$1. For each paper initially retrieved, the LLM generated a textual justification of its relevance, accompanied by a numeric confidence score (0–100%). Figure 3 illustrates how varying this configurable confidence threshold affects AI classification. At lower thresholds, the AI model becomes overly inclusive, resulting in high false-positive (type I) rates. Conversely, at higher thresholds, the model significantly reduces false positives but at the expense of excluding relevant papers (higher type II errors). A practical compromise was achieved at a threshold of 50%, balancing recall and precision, thereby reducing the manual workload, especially during the title and abstract screening stages. The differences between human-led and AI-assisted selection outcomes (Table 1) result directly from this prioritization of recall. In this case study, the AI-assisted method retained more papers at intermediate steps (826 vs. 190 after title/abstract screening, and 166 vs. 60 after full-text screening). While this broader selection led to lower precision compared to the strictly human approach, it reduced the risk of prematurely excluding relevant studies. It should be noted that assuming human selections as being the ground truth is practical for evaluation purposes but may overlook certain biases or inconsistencies in manual screening. Importantly, our approach retains human validation in the final stages, ensuring overall methodological rigor and interpretative validity.

During the *Analyze* phase, AI substantially supported thematic synthesis by performing initial open coding based on full-text excerpts. Leveraging LLM-generated coding alongside associated confidence ratings, we systematically extracted key thematic concepts from the selected literature. Human researchers subsequently validated, refined, and adjusted these AI-generated codes to ensure conceptual clarity, accuracy, and alignment with domain-specific interpretations. After filtering excerpts by a high-confidence threshold ($\geq 94\%$), we further processed the AI-generated open codes using an LLM-driven axial coding procedure, identifying recurrent thematic patterns across the literature corpus. This iterative human-AI collaborative process resulted in a set of AI-suggested conceptual

Fig. 3. AI-assisted paper selection and error analysis. Upper panel: Fraction of papers selected (green circles) and excluded (orange squares) at varying AI confidence thresholds. Lower panel: Corresponding type I (false positives) and type II (false negatives) error rates at each threshold, computed against human selections as ground truth.

categories. We then critically compared these categories to the established conceptual framework from our previous human-led SLR to assess thematic alignment, novelty, and comprehensiveness, which indicated a strong correspondence between AI-suggested and human-defined thematic patterns, as illustrated in Table 4. Eight of the original nine human-defined themes were effectively covered by the AI-generated categories, demonstrating, in this instance, the AI’s ability to capture complex thematic structures accurately. However, the AI’s classification highlighted notable points requiring human refinement. First, the AI combined the previously distinct human-defined concepts *Personalized user engagement* and *User interface and experience* into a single broader category labeled *User-Centric Design and Comfort*. This AI-driven merger underscores the importance of human judgment in explicitly determining the appropriate granularity of thematic categories, ensuring theoretical clarity and interpretive coherence. Second, the AI introduced two additional thematic categories not explicitly identified by human reviewers: *Feedback and Monitoring Systems* and *Sustainability and Efficiency in Design*. Upon human evaluation, the latter was assessed as overly generic, effectively encompassing the overall theme of the review itself, thus requiring refinement or potential removal by human experts to maintain conceptual specificity. Conversely, the category *Feedback and Monitoring Systems*, although partially overlapping with existing human-defined themes, contributed valuable additional insights and was therefore retained after careful human consideration and refinement. To allow comparability, we then mapped the excerpts identified by the AI to the original set of concepts. Figure 4 visually summarizes the

alignment and differences between human- and AI-identified thematic patterns, clearly demonstrating the supportive role AI can play in conceptual synthesis, alongside the essential interpretive and critical oversight provided by human researchers. Overall, the results show a substantial overlap in thematic coverage across both approaches, particularly for core themes such as predictive analytics, real-time monitoring, and strategies for efficiency. However, some deviations are evident. For instance, the AI-based coding exhibited broader coverage of interoperability and context-aware features, while the human analysis placed greater emphasis on user engagement. We attribute these differences primarily to the LLM’s tendency to apply broader conceptual mappings based on surface-level term similarity rather than contextual or theoretical nuance. This may lead to slight over-representation of technical or functional aspects, while more context-sensitive themes (e.g., user engagement or privacy implications) require careful human interpretation and validation. Importantly, these deviations do not constitute methodological flaws but rather highlight the complementary strengths and limitations of AI-driven coding. Our method addresses this challenge by ensuring that AI suggestions are grounded in validated source excerpts and by explicitly integrating human oversight into all stages of coding and theme development. In practice, this means that AI accelerates the identification and initial organization of thematic patterns, while human researchers refine, contextualize, and ensure the interpretative coherence of the final thematic structure.

Fig. 4. Comparison of thematic patterns in the human-led SLR and AI-assisted SLR

5 Discussion and Conclusion

This study presented an AI-augmented SLR framework and illustrated its application through a comparative case study against a traditional human-led SLR.

We systematically applied LLMs across key stages of the SLR process, including paper selection, thematic analysis, and conceptual synthesis. The results of this case study suggest that AI can effectively augment multiple stages of the SLR process, particularly in initial screening and thematic analysis. The integration of AI notably reduces manual workload, cognitive burden, and overall review duration, echoing and extending prior exploratory findings [35, 25]. At moderate confidence thresholds, AI-assisted selection achieves an optimal balance between type I (false positive) and type II (false negative) errors, closely aligning with human judgment. Furthermore, AI-supported thematic coding yields complementary insights, highlighting concepts and thematic connections that might otherwise remain underexplored in purely manual reviews. Nonetheless, our results underscore the critical importance of continued human oversight, especially given AI’s tendency toward conservative relevance assessments, to ensure rigorous methodological quality and interpretive validity. Our study thus aligns with and empirically validates prior qualitative cautions regarding AI’s limitations, such as potential biases, reduced transparency, and interpretive risks [25, 30].

Our findings have several theoretical implications. First, this study demonstrates that AI tools can significantly augment traditional SLR methodologies, particularly in terms of scalability and efficiency, without compromising methodological rigor. These results substantiate previous qualitative and exploratory claims about AI’s potential [24, 28, 35], providing concrete empirical evidence regarding the practical effectiveness of AI-assisted literature screening and thematic analysis. By systematically integrating AI across all phases, our framework extends beyond previous studies that primarily focused on individual phases [27, 38] or provided qualitative demonstrations without systematic validation [30]. Second, extending previous literature [25], the identified complementary thematic insights provided by AI-driven coding suggest that AI can streamline existing methodological procedures and also enhance theoretical discovery. Third, while AI can reshape the epistemic practices of literature reviews, we find that careful human oversight and interpretation remain indispensable to avoid epistemic flattening, aligning with previous findings [25]. Fourth, by explicitly delineating human and AI responsibilities (as depicted in Figure 1), our framework contributes to clearer methodological standards and transparency in AI-augmented SLRs, addressing calls from prior literature [35, 30].

The practical implications of our study are substantial for researchers conducting SLRs. By demonstrating robust accuracy and balanced type I and type II error rates, our case study offers practical guidance for effectively calibrating AI assistance. Applying AI for initial screening and thematic identification can significantly reduce manual workload during these labor-intensive phases. This aligns with previous research [28, 38], reinforcing the viability of hybrid workflows that blend AI-driven augmentation with human oversight. Our empirical insights also suggest practices for human-AI collaboration, highlighting the need for iterative validation, threshold calibration, and careful interpretive oversight. Given AI’s observed conservative bias, researchers are advised to initially adopt moderate thresholds and subsequently refine their approach iteratively based

on intermediate validations. Additionally, the complementary thematic insights identified by AI indicate that researchers can employ AI not merely for efficiency but also as a proactive means of uncovering theoretical insights and enhancing the depth and scope of literature reviews. Lastly, this research offers a notable managerial implication: While practitioners might not necessarily conduct or publish scientific SLRs themselves, the proposed AI-augmented framework could empower them to more effectively and efficiently engage with academic literature. In this way, practitioners can gain enhanced and timely insights into academic research, thus making scholarly knowledge more accessible in practical contexts.

Despite these promising findings, several limitations of our study warrant careful consideration. First, our illustration and evaluation focused on a single SLR domain, potentially limiting generalizability to other research contexts. Future studies should explore the applicability and robustness of our AI-augmented framework across diverse research topics and interdisciplinary domains. Second, LLMs inherently depend on the quality and comprehensiveness of their underlying training data. Thus, biases, inaccuracies, or gaps present in training datasets may propagate into AI-assisted SLR processes, underscoring the critical role of human validation and interpretative oversight. We deliberately used `GPT-4o-mini`, a cost-effective and fast model, making our AI-augmented method highly accessible to a broad range of researchers, even with minimal resources. However, future studies may explore the use of larger (and somewhat costlier) models, potentially improving accuracy or synthesis quality. Third, while our study evaluated AI's impact on efficiency, accuracy, and thematic alignment, additional qualitative investigations into researcher experiences, perceptions of cognitive burden, and trust in AI-generated outcomes would further enrich the understanding of effective human-AI collaboration. Future research should aim to extend our investigation by applying the framework to diverse SLRs across various disciplines to assess its broader applicability and robustness. This would also involve exploring comparisons against other AI-assisted SLR tools or more standardized benchmarks where feasible and appropriate for specific components of our framework, to further contextualize its performance.

In conclusion, this study introduced an AI-augmented SLR framework and provided initial empirical evidence from a comparative case study, suggesting its practical viability and theoretical robustness of integrating AI into SLRs. The proposed framework balances automation with human oversight, significantly enhancing efficiency and thematic exploration while maintaining scholarly rigor. Through iterative validation and human-AI role delineation, researchers can effectively use AI technologies to manage the growing volume of academic literature and deepen thematic insights. We thus contribute meaningfully to ongoing theoretical discussions and practical advancements in SLR methodologies.

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Appendix

Table 1. Comparison of selected papers per step between the human SLR and the AI-augmented SLR

Step	Human	Human-AI
Search	$n = 2518$	$n = 2518$
Screen titles/abstracts	$n = 190$	$n = 826$
Screen full texts	$n = 60$	$n = 166$

Table 2. Comparison of human-designed and AI-generated search strings

Human-designed	AI-generated
("artificial intelligence" OR "AI" OR "machine learning" OR "ML")	("Artificial Intelligence" OR AI OR "Machine Learning" OR "Intelligent Systems" OR "Intelligent Assistant" OR "Assistance Systems" OR "Conversational Agent" OR Chatbot)
AND (("energy" AND (sav* OR efficien*)) OR "green" OR "sustainability")	AND (Sustainability OR "Environmental Sustainability" OR "Energy Efficiency" OR "Resource Efficiency" OR "Energy Conservation" OR "Sustainable Consumption" OR "Green IT")
AND ("smart home" OR "smart living" OR "smart building")	AND ("Smart Home" OR "Smart Living" OR "Home Automation" OR "Smart Environment" OR "Ambient Intelligence" OR "Connected Home")
AND (app* OR platform* OR ecosystem* OR "statistics" OR "guideline" OR "framework")	AND (Requirement OR Requirements OR "Design Principle" OR "Design Guidelines" OR "Design Criteria" OR "System Requirements" OR "User Needs" OR "Functional Requirements" OR "Non-functional Requirements")

Table 3. Prompts employed in our AI-augmented SLR.

<p>Prompt 1: Screen titles/abstracts</p> <p>You are assisting with selecting relevant papers for a systematic literature review (SLR). The research question (RQ) of this SLR is: <code>"{research_question}"</code> <code>{short_explanation}</code></p> <p>You will be asked to explain the paper's potential relevance and then provide a numerical confidence score (0-100) for its relevance.</p> <p>Title: <code>{title}</code> Abstract: <code>{abstract}</code></p> <p>Based solely on the title and abstract, please explain briefly how relevant this paper might be for the SLR described above. Then, provide an integer between 0 and 100 that reflects your confidence in the paper's relevance.</p>
<p>Prompt 2: Screen full texts</p> <p>You are analyzing full texts for a systematic literature review (SLR). For each excerpt that is relevant to the following research question: <code>"{research_question}"</code> <code>{short_explanation}</code></p> <p>Extract a list of relevant excerpts. Each excerpt must include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The original text (verbatim), - An open code summarizing its thematic content (according to grounded theory), - A confidence score between 0 and 100 estimating its relevance. <p>Full text: <code>{markdown_text}</code></p>
<p>Prompt 3: Open coding</p> <p>You are supporting a systematic literature review using grounded theory. You have been given a list of open-coded excerpts (open codes and supporting text). Your task is to identify recurring patterns (concepts) among these codes. Return a structured list of concepts. Each concept must include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A short title - A brief description summarizing the theme or pattern observed across excerpts with similar open codes. <p>Excerpts: <code>{excerpt_blocks}</code></p>
<p>Prompt 4: Mapping</p> <p>You are analyzing excerpts from a literature review. Your task is to assign each excerpt to the most appropriate concept from the list below. Return only the concept title that best matches the excerpt.</p> <p>Excerpt: <code>{excerpt}</code> Concepts: <code>{concept_list}</code></p> <p>Which concept best fits this excerpt? Respond with the title only.</p>

Table 4. Comparison of thematic patterns: human-led vs. AI-assisted SLR

Human-led patterns	AI-assisted patterns
Predictive analytics and ML underscores the importance of advanced algorithms for optimizing energy consumption and detecting anomalies.	Predictive and Data-Driven Approaches emphasize using predictive models and data analytics to anticipate user behavior, energy needs, and system performance, enabling proactive management and optimization.
Privacy and security emphasizes the need for robust data protection mechanisms to ensure user trust.	Security, Privacy, and Data Management stress the importance of addressing user privacy and data security concerns as fuzzy logic, predictive controls, and user inputs to ensure optimal energy efficiency and comfort.
Context-aware features focus on systems that adapt to user behaviors and environmental changes to improve efficiency and comfort.	Advanced Control Systems capture the development and implementation of sophisticated control systems, such as HVAC, that leverage fuzzy logic, predictive controls, and user inputs to ensure optimal energy efficiency and comfort.
Real-time monitoring and analysis highlights the significance of continuous data collection and analysis for informed decision-making.	Dynamic System Response focuses on the ability of systems, especially in smart home environments, to respond and adapt dynamically to unforeseen and shifting conditions in real-time.
Interoperability and scalability stresses the importance of flexible and extensible systems.	Integration and Coordination of Technologies explores the integration of multiple technologies, such as AI, IoT, and machine learning, to coordinate smart home systems and improve their efficiency and adaptability.
Strategies for efficiency discusses strategies for improving sustainable energy use and integrating renewable sources.	Energy Efficiency and Management highlights the importance of optimizing energy usage through advanced algorithms, predictive models, AI, and IoT, striving to make energy consumption more efficient and sustainable.
Personalized user engagement explores methods to tailor user experiences and encourage energy-saving behaviors. User interface and experience focuses on creating user-friendly interfaces that facilitate engagement and understanding.	User-Centric Design and Comfort (<i>merged by AI</i>) revolves around designing systems that focus on user needs, preferences, and comfort, ensuring that technology serves human requirements effectively without compromising on user experience.
Other behavioral and social aspects examine strategies to influence user behavior and build trust.	Behavioural Interventions and Nudges use digital nudges and eco-feedback systems to influence and guide user behavior towards more sustainable practices without restricting freedom of choice.
(<i>No direct human equivalent</i>)	Feedback and Monitoring Systems discuss the use of feedback mechanisms and monitoring systems to improve the awareness of energy consumption behaviors and enhance the performance of smart building systems.
(<i>No direct human equivalent</i>)	Sustainability and Efficiency in Design (<i>AI suggested, overly broad</i>) highlight strategies and technological solutions aimed at promoting sustainability and energy efficiency, particularly through innovations in IoT and smart technologies.